

Divalent cobalt, nickel and copper chelates of macrocycle derived from 2,3-butanedione and its dihydrazide

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Manuscript received 11 July 2001, revised 5 April 2002, accepted 17 June 2002

Divalent cobalt, nickel and copper salts reacts *in situ* with 2,3-butanedione and its dihydrazide to form complexes containing a 16-membered tetradentate macrocyclic ligand. The complexes derived from 2,3-butanedione and its dihydrazide may be represented as $[M(C_{16}H_{24}N_8)X_2]$, where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} and $X = Cl, Br, NO_3, NCS$.

Some work has been initiated on macrocyclic metal chelates derived from aromatic diamines and dicarbonyl compounds^{1,2} and also from dihydrazide and dicarbonyl compounds³, but there is no report on metal chelates of macrocycles derived from dicarbonyl compound and its own dihydrazide. Therefore, the divalent cobalt, nickel and copper chelates of macrocycle derived from 2,3-butanedione and its dihydrazide were undertaken.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data show the formula of macrocyclic complexes as $[M(C_{16}H_{24}N_8)X_2]$, where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} and $X = Cl, Br, NO_3, NCS$. The tests for anions are positive only after decomposing the complexes with conc. HNO_3 , indicating their presence inside the coordination sphere.

All the complexes do not exhibit any IR bands at ~ 3400 – 3200 cm^{-1} (NH_2). The absence of free carbonyl band ($\sim 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicates that this group is not present in the metal chelates⁴. The absence of stretching and bending vibrations of $C=O$ at ~ 1525 and 1280 cm^{-1} , substantiates the absence of CO group⁵. The strong bands appearing as doublet at ~ 1595 – 1630 cm^{-1} (CN azomethine) point towards the coordinated azomethine group^{2,4}. Thus, both the NH_2 group of dihydrazide have condensed with carbonyl groups of 2,3-butanedione and give rise N_8 arrangement of azomethine nitrogen atoms equally suitable for coordination. This contention finds support by the appearance of bands at $\sim 2925, 1360, 1275$ and 675 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{CH_3} , $\nu_{C=CH_3}$, $\delta_{sym}CH_3$ and ring deformation modes of 2,3-butanedione moieties, respectively⁵. The bands at ~ 1570 ($C=O$), 1530 (bonded CO) and 660 cm^{-1} (CH_3C-O) are not observed in the spectra of these complexes⁵. The ab-

sence of these vibrations again points out that carbonyl groups of 2,3-butanedione have condensed with NH_2 group of its dihydrazide³.

However, the macrocycles possess hydrazinic ($=N-N=$) and azomethine ($C=N$) groups. The position of ν_{CN} can be ascertained by comparing the spectra of any hydrazide and that of corresponding hydrazones⁶. All the derivatives of hydrazides including hydrazones show characteristic frequencies due to $N-N$ groups. Therefore, in the metal chelates coordination takes place through four azomethine nitrogen atoms forming square-planar four six-membered chelate rings, anions being on axial position making the environment of six-coordinate octahedral around the metal atom.

The nitrate complexes of all the macrocycles exhibit new bands at $\sim 1240, 1020$ and 870 – 875 cm^{-1} , consistent with the monodentate nature of this groups. This is substantiated by the small splitting of bands ($\nu_1 + \nu_2$) appearing at ~ 1765 – 1770 and 1740 – 1750 cm^{-1} and show that nitrate group is monodentate in nature in these complexes. The thiocyanato complexes exhibit strong bands at ~ 2120 (CN), 815 (CS) and 480 cm^{-1} (NCS) and are in accordance with the monodentate N -bonded thiocyanato group⁵.

Magnetic moments of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes (at 298 K) are 3.15–3.30, 4.58–4.70 and 1.74–1.78 B.M., respectively. All these values indicate spin-free nature of these metal ions and are consistent with six-coordinate octahedral geometry around the metal atom. These values also exclude dimeric or polymeric nature of the complexes⁷.

Cobalt complexes :

The electronic spectra exhibited bands at 7900–8920 (ν_1) and 15380–17540 (ν_2) with a broad band envelope $\sim 21000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) showing almost two discernable bands

at $\sim 18200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The spectra of the complexes are comparable to those reported to be distorted octahedral⁸. Thus, assuming the effective symmetry to be D_{4h} , various bands can be assigned to as ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (~ 8000), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (16000) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (~ 20000). The assignment of first spin-allowed band ${}^4A_{2g}(F)$ seems plausible since the first band appears approximately at half the energy of the visible band⁸. This is true in view of the ν_2/ν_1 ratio which lies towards the lower side of 2.1–2.2 and is consistent with the accuracy of the assignment. The values of various ligand field parameters are given in Table 1.

Nickel complexes :

The solution spectra of the nickel complexes show three strong bands at 11750–12200, 16450–17150 and 27600–28250 cm^{-1} with a well discernable shoulder at 9500–10300 cm^{-1} on the low energy side of the first band. The spectral bands are well within the range observed for hexacoordinate octahedral complexes reported earlier^{2,9}. The first two bands result from the splitting of one band and can be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_{1g}(\nu_1)$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}(\nu_2)$ assuming the effective symmetry to D_{4h} (component of ${}^3T_{2g}$ in O_h symmetry⁸). The other two higher bands can be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}(P)$, respectively, in order of increasing energy. The intense higher energy band at ~ 35000

cm^{-1} may be due to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition of C=N group of the ligand. Many bands do not show any regular pattern and seem to be anion independent. The spectra are consistent with distorted octahedral nature of these complexes and calculated Dt, Dq, DT and DQ values¹⁰ are given in Table 1.

Copper complexes :

The spectra of the copper complexes exhibit bands at 17700–19550 cm^{-1} with a shoulder on low energy side (14500–17000 cm^{-1}) and that these complexes are distorted octahedral¹¹. The spectral bands of the complexes shift to a slightly higher energy side in the order : $\text{NCS} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{Br} > \text{Cl}$, i.e. in order of weakening interaction of the metal atom with anions. Assuming tetragonal distortion in the molecule, energy level sequence for these complexes may be drawn as $d_{x^2-y^2} > d_{z^2} > d_{xy} > d_{xz} > d_{yz}$ and the shoulder can be assigned to $d_{z^2}, d_{x^2-y^2} ({}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g})$ and the broad band contains both the $d_{xy}-d_{x^2-y^2} ({}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g)$ and $d_{xy}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} ({}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g})$ transition¹². The separation of the spectral bands of these complexes is of the order $\sim 2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is consistent with the proposed geometry of the complexes¹³. Therefore, it may be concluded that all the complexes formed by macrocycles with Cu^{II} metals are distorted octahedral.

Table 1. Magnetic and electronic spectral data of divalent Ni and Co complexes

Compd.	λ_{max} cm^{-1}	Dq ^{xy}	Dq ^z	Dt	DT	DS	DQ	DQ ^{xy}	DQ ^z	DT/DQ	μ_{eff} B.M
[Ni(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)Cl ₂]	10700, 11710, 18180, 27836, 34850	1171	969	115	1560	11690	30353	32199	26661	0.051	3.30
[Ni(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)Br ₂]	10720, 11760 18220, 28200, 35000	1176	968	119	1615	11480	30427	32338	26605	0.053	3.25
[Ni(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)(NO ₃) ₂]	10660, 11780, 18280, 28320, 35200	1178	952	121	1640	11550	30450	32390	26568	0.054	3.15
[Ni(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)(NCS) ₂]	10560, 11690, 18250, 28280, 34780	1169	943	129	1750	11480	30073	32144	25931	0.058	3.28
			Dq		B		β		ν_2/ν_1		μ_{eff} B.M.
[Co(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)Cl ₂]	8630, 15930, 18620, 21570		1078		810		0.83		1.85		4.59
[Co(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)Br ₂]	8250, 16250, 18480, 21620		1031		820		0.84		1.97		4.68
[Cu(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)(NO ₃) ₂]	8570, 15750, 18540, 21490		1071		808		0.83		1.84		4.63
[Co(C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₈)(NCS) ₂]	8750, 16120, 18460, 21500		1094		793		0.82		1.84		4.57

The far-IR spectra of the macrocyclic complexes showed various band at $\sim 425\text{--}440$ (Co-N), $445\text{--}465$ (Ni-N) and $475\text{--}515\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Cu-N) of azomethine vibrations¹⁴. These values are well within the range reported for six-coordinated octahedral complexes¹⁴. The spectra of the halo complexes showed various new bands assignable to metal-halogen vibrations. The bands at $\sim 330\text{--}335$ (Co-Cl), $280\text{--}315$ (Ni-Cl) and $270\text{--}275\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Cu-Cl) are consistent with octahedral geometry of the chelates¹⁵. Similar bands were observed for the bromo complexes of the macrocycle at ~ 220 (Co-Br) and ~ 215 (Ni-Br). The coordination of nitrate and thiocyanate group is further substantiated by the appearance of bands at $225\text{--}240\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ of NO_2 and at $260\text{--}285\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu_{\text{M-NCS}}$ of NCS group¹⁶, respectively.

Experimental

2,3-Butanedione and hydrazine hydrate (B.D.H.) were used. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. All solvents were of high purity and distilled before use. A mixture of methanolic solution of 2,3-butanedione (0.02 mol) and 2,3-butanedionedihydrazide (0.02 mol in 100 ml methanol) was refluxed for 2 h. A methanolic solution of the metal salt (0.01 mol) was then added to it followed by a few drops of glacial acetic acid and refluxing continued for 6 h. The mixture was then concentrated to half of its volume and kept in desiccator for 3–4 days. The dark crystals that separated out were washed with methanol, acetone, ether and dried *in vacuo* (yield $\sim 30\%$). The nitrate complexes were prepared from the metal nitrates. Bromo and thiocyanato salts of these metals were prepared by adding slowly potassium bromide or thiocyanate solutions to an ethanolic solution of the metal chloride with stirring and filtering off potassium chloride or ammonium chloride.

All the complexes showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

Metals were determined by standard EDTA methods. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by the Gouy method using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. IR spectra at $4000\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in KBr were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and in nujol at $650\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a

Beckmann IR-12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Cary 14 spectrophotometer. A Toshniwal CL01/01 conductivity bridge was used.

References

1. V. B. Rana, P. Singh, D. P. Singh and M. P. Teotia, *Polyhedron*, 1982, **1**, 377; *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1981, **6**, 36; 1982, **7**, 174; D. P. Singh and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 266.
2. D. P. Singh, N. Shishodia, B. P. Yadav and V. B. Rana, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2229.
3. V. B. Rana, S. P. Ratra, D. P. Singh and M. P. Teotia, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 115.
4. S. Chandra and R. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 1003.
5. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 2nd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
6. V. B. Rana, S. K. Sahni and S. K. Sangal, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 1490; S. K. Sahni, S. P. Gupta, S. K. Sangal and V. B. Rana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 200.
7. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 37.
8. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
9. A. S. Bull, R. B. Martin and R. J. P. Williams in "Electronic Aspects of Biochemistry", ed. B. Pullman, Academic, New York, 1964.
10. J. C. Donini, B. R. Hollebhone and A. B. P. Lever, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **22**, 225.
11. M. J. M. Campbell and R. Grezeskoviak, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1969, **5**, 27.
12. L. F. Lindoy and D. H. Busch, *Prep. Inorg. React.*, 1971, **6**, 1.
13. A. B. P. Lever and E. Mantovani, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 817.
14. J. R. Farrero, "Low Frequency of Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
15. V. B. Rana, S. K. Sahni, M. P. Swami, P. C. Jain and A. K. Srivastava, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 176.
16. D. A. Baldwin, A. B. P. Lever and R. V. Parish, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 107.